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3 **Unraveling the phylogenetic relationships of the extinct bovid**
4 ***Myotragus balearicus* Bate 1909 from the Balearic Islands**

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33 **Abstract**

34 *Myotragus balearicus* was the last living representative of an extinct caprine
35 lineage endemic to the Balearic Islands (Western Mediterranean), which became extinct
36 following the arrival of humans around 4,300 years ago. The tribal attribution of
37 *Myotragus* based on morphological analyses has been complicated due to its unusual
38 morphological characteristics, though most studies agree on its inclusion within Caprini
39 (also including modern sheep and goats). Analyses of short fragments of ancient
40 mitochondrial DNA have suggested *Ovis* (comprising extant sheep) as sister taxon to
41 *Myotragus*, although other authors have suggested alternative placements within
42 Caprini using the same data. In the present study, we present a complete high-depth
43 mitochondrial genome of *M. balearicus*, which allowed us to test the previously
44 proposed *Ovis/Myotragus* clade and revealed a closer relationship between *Myotragus*
45 and the takin (*Budorcas taxicolor*). The results of our molecular clock analyses
46 suggested that the split between *Myotragus* and *Budorcas* occurred around 7.1 Mya,
47 which is compatible with the arrival of the ancestor of *Myotragus* to the Balearic
48 Islands during the Messinian Salinity Crisis (5.97–5.33 Mya). We also conducted a
49 preliminary phylogeographic analysis of *M. balearicus* in Mallorca, which revealed
50 weak spatial and temporal structure within the population during the Holocene.

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55 **Keywords:** *Myotragus balearicus*; Quaternary; Ancient DNA; Western Europe;

56 Balearic Islands; Phylogeny, Mitochondrial Genomes; Paleogeography

57

58 **1. Introduction**

59 Bovids – including extant goats, sheep, antelopes, and cattle – are relatively rare
60 components of endemic island communities, as they are generally unsuited for long-
61 distance overwater dispersal (Palombo et al., 2006; Van der Geer et al, 2010; Rozzi and
62 Palombo, 2014). Nevertheless, three extinct lineages clearly identified as members of
63 the bovid subfamily Antilopinae [*sensu* Hassanin and Douzery (1999) and Ropiquet
64 and Hassanin (2005a)] have been recorded in the Mediterranean islands, all attributable
65 to the tribe Caprini (sheep and their allies): 1) *Nesogoral* from the Late Pliocene to
66 Early Pleistocene of Sardinia (Italy) (Palombo et al., 2013); 2) an undescribed species
67 from the Early Pliocene of Eivissa (Moyà-Solà et al., 1984, 1999); and 3) *Myotragus*
68 from the Early Pliocene to Holocene of Mallorca and from the Late Pliocene/Early
69 Pleistocene to Holocene of Menorca (Balearic Islands, Spain) (Bover et al., 2014; Mas
70 et al., 2018). *Myotragus* was endemic to the Eastern Balearic Islands (Western
71 Mediterranean Sea) and its ancestor presumably dispersed to the islands during the
72 Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC) between 5.97 and 5.33 Million years ago (Mya;
73 Krigsman et al., 1999; Manzi et al., 2013), when the Balearic Islands would have been
74 connected by land to mainland Europe (Mas et al., 2018). The *Myotragus* fossil record
75 has been widely studied on the two islands it inhabited, Mallorca and Menorca (Fig. 1),
76 revealing an anagenetic lineage comprising up to six chronospecies in Mallorca and two
77 in Menorca (see Bover et al., 2008, 2010, 2014; Mas et al., 2018). *Myotragus*
78 *balearicus*, the terminal member of the lineage, was probably driven extinct on both
79 islands soon after the first human arrival to these islands, around 4,300 years ago
80 (Bover et al., 2016). However, despite its relatively recent extinction (making it
81 amenable to ancient DNA—aDNA—analysis) and its abundance in Balearic fossil
82 deposits, many questions remain regarding the evolutionary history of *Myotragus*.

83 Specimens attributed to the chronospecies comprising the *Myotragus* lineage
84 exhibit drastic morphological changes since the Pliocene, including: a decrease in
85 overall body mass, an increase of limb bone robustness, a decrease of bone length
86 (especially in stylopodium and autopodium elements), a progressive reduction in
87 number and size of incisiform and premolar teeth, and a reduction of brain size and
88 sense organs (*e.g.*, Alcover et al., 1981; Köhler and Moyà-Solà, 2004; Bover and
89 Tolosa, 2005). These changes, unique to *Myotragus*, have made it challenging to
90 resolve the phylogenetic placement of *Myotragus* within Caprini based on
91 morphological data alone. Andrews (1914) suggested that a new subfamily,
92 Myotraginae, would need to be erected to accommodate the genus, although he did not
93 preclude its attribution to the rupicaprine (Naemorhadine) clade. Other authors included
94 *Myotragus* in the Rupicaprini (*e.g.*, Alcover et al., 1981) or Nemorhaedini tribes
95 (Gliozzi and Malatesta, 1980). More specifically, Bover et al. (2010) suggested that the
96 Late Miocene ancestor of *Myotragus* would likely be from the European mainland,
97 closely related to the late Turolian-earliest Ruscianian (MN 13/14) species *Aragoral*
98 *mudejar* and *Norbertia hellenica*.

99 Lalueza-Fox et al. (2000) attempted to use aDNA analyses to shed light on the
100 phylogenetic position of *Myotragus*. They sequenced a 95-bp fragment of the
101 mitochondrial cytochrome b gene (mtDNA cytb) and suggested an affinity between *M.*
102 *balearicus* and the takin (*Budorcas taxicolor*), which at the time was considered the
103 sister taxon to *Ovis* (including the domestic sheep). While the *B. taxicolor* cytb
104 sequence was later found to be chimeric (Ropiquet and Hassanin, 2005a), a close
105 relationship between *Myotragus* and *Ovis* was subsequently suggested by analyses of
106 longer DNA sequences: 338 bp of cytb (Lalueza-Fox et al., 2002), a combination of the
107 complete cytb gene (1,143 bp) and a 305-bp fragment of the 12S rRNA gene (Lalueza-

108 Fox et al., 2005a, b), and 1,987 mitochondrial and nuclear nucleotides from shotgun
109 sequencing (Ramírez et al., 2009). Other authors have placed *M. balearicus* as sister-
110 taxon to the extant members of Caprini (Agnarsson and May-Collado, 2008) or in an
111 unresolved position (Bibi et al., 2012). This lack of phylogenetic resolution based on
112 short DNA fragments is unsurprising, as the genera comprising Caprini are generally
113 considered to have undergone a rapid radiation at the end of the Miocene (*e.g.*,
114 Hassanin et al., 1998; Ropiquet and Hassanin, 2005a). More complete mitochondrial
115 sequence data may clarify the phylogenetic position of *Myotragus* within Caprini.

116 In this paper we present 13 complete (or partial) mitochondrial genome
117 sequences from Mallorcan specimens of *Myotragus balearicus*. We use these data to re-
118 evaluate the phylogenetic position of *Myotragus*, and test the hypothesis that their
119 ancestor dispersed to the Balearic Islands during the MSC.

120

121 **2. Materials and methods**

122 **2.1. Materials**

123 Forty-nine bones of *Myotragus balearicus* were selected from collections
124 obtained from 22 Late Pleistocene to Holocene deposits in Mallorca during cave
125 exploration campaigns spanning the 1960s to 1980s and excavation campaigns from the
126 1990s to the 2000s (Table S1). Specimens were curated at the collection of the Institut
127 Mediterrani d'Estudis Avançats (IMEDEA) in Esporles (Mallorca), and at the Museu
128 Balear de Ciències Naturals (MBCN) in Sóller (Mallorca). When possible, we sampled
129 elements from one side of the skeleton only from deposits with multiple individuals, to
130 avoid analyzing the same individual multiple times. No direct chronological
131 information was initially available for the samples (except for sample ACAD13102
132 from Cova des Mort in Cabrera, Bover and Alcover 2003; UtC-6517, 4785±40 BP,

133 3650-3380 2σ cal BC), so samples were selected according to the general preservation
134 state of the bones/teeth. Some bones and teeth were selected from caves that had
135 already yielded DNA from *Myotragus* fossil remains: Coveta des Gorgs and Cova
136 Estreta (see Lalueza-Fox et al., 2000, 2002, 2005a,b; Ramírez et al., 2009).

137

138 **2.2. DNA Extraction**

139 DNA from our *Myotragus balearicus* samples was extracted in the dedicated
140 ancient DNA laboratory at the Australian Centre for Ancient DNA (ACAD) at the
141 University of Adelaide (Australia). Negative controls were extracted alongside each
142 extraction batch of samples.

143 Extracts from all samples were performed using a previously published silica-
144 based method (Brotherton et al., 2013). Briefly, approximately 1 mm of the exterior
145 surface was removed using a Dremel rotary tool with a cutting disc, then bone
146 fragments were powdered using a Braun Mikrodismembrator U (B. Braun Biotech
147 International, Germany) with an 8 mm tungsten ball for 5 seconds at 3000 revolutions
148 per minute. The amount of bone powder obtained ranged between 90 and 250 mg (see
149 Table S1). The powder of each sample was decalcified and digested overnight at 55 °C
150 on a rotary wheel in 4 mL 0.5 M EDTA (pH 8.0), 200 μ L of 10 % SDS, and 40 μ L of
151 20 mg/mL Proteinase K. DNA extraction was performed using a modified QG buffer
152 (QIAGEN) and suspended silicon dioxide. Samples were then purified using 80%
153 ethanol and eluted in TLE buffer (10 mM Tris, 0.1 mM EDTA pH 8.0) obtaining a final
154 volume of 200 μ L of DNA extract (100 μ L if less than 100 mg of starting bone
155 powder).

156 Two modified extraction methods were used to re-extract sample ACAD13066
157 (the original extraction is hereafter referred to as extract “A”). A modified extraction

158 protocol based on Dabney et al. (2013) was used as one repeat extraction of sample
159 ACAD13066 (hereafter, extract “B”). One mL of the decalcification/digestion buffer
160 (0.45M EDTA, 0.25 mg/ml Proteinase K) was added to 100 mg of cortical bone powder
161 of this sample and incubated overnight on a rotary wheel at 37 °C. The supernatant was
162 then collected after centrifugation and bound to suspended silicon dioxide with addition
163 of 13.6 mL of PB buffer (QIAGEN), 7 µL of Tween-20, and 420 µL of 3M sodium
164 acetate. After purification with 80% ethanol, DNA was eluted with 100 µL of TLE
165 buffer.

166 The second re-extraction of sample ACAD13066 (hereafter, extract “C”) used a
167 modified version of the previous (“B”) re-extraction method. To increase the efficiency
168 of the bone digestion step, 110 mg of bone powder from ACAD13066 was predigested
169 in 1 mL of 0.5M EDTA during 1 hour at room temperature. Then the
170 decalcification/digestion step was performed as for extract B using the same digestion
171 buffer but increasing the temperature to 55 °C. The bone powder was completely
172 digested after this overnight incubation and the supernatant was processed following
173 the protocol mentioned above for extract B.

174

175 **2.3. Screening and radiocarbon dating**

176 To screen our samples for DNA preservation, we attempted to amplify a 96-97
177 bp fragment of mitochondrial 12S using primers Mamm 12S_E (Forward) and Mammal
178 12S_H (Reverse) (Macqueen et al., 2010). Two µL of extract were used in each PCR
179 reaction following a previously described protocol (*e.g.*, Bover et al., 2018a). PCR
180 amplicons were purified using Agencourt AMPure XP magnetic beads (Beckman
181 Coulter) following the manufacturer’s protocol. Both forward and reverse strands were
182 sequenced using the BigDye Terminator Kit v3.1 (Applied Biosystems), with the dye

183 terminator removed using the Agencourt CleanSEQ magnetic particle solution
184 (Beckman Coulter) and each strand sequenced on a 3130xl Genetic Analyzer (Applied
185 Biosystems). All extraction blank controls failed to amplify. Fifteen of our 49 samples
186 yielded bovid sequences that did not appear to derive from contamination as they were
187 identified as *Myotragus balearicus* in the BLASTn analysis (Table S1). These samples
188 originated from six caves in the northern range of the island, the so-called Serra de
189 Tramuntana, and are located above 300 meters above sea level (m.a.s.l) (Avenc de Fra
190 Rafel, Avenc des Gorg Blau, Coveta des Gorgs, Cova de s'Olla, Cova Estreta, and
191 Cova des Màrmol). Ten of the samples were collected from the same cave, Coveta des
192 Gorgs (Escorca), a small cave located at 800 m.a.s.l (Fig. 1). Only 15 positive samples
193 were subjected to downstream analyses (with the exception of ACAD13139, which was
194 subjected to further analysis despite a negative PCR result because of the good visual
195 preservation of the bone).

196 Following screening, we sent 13 *M. balearicus* bones for radiocarbon dating at
197 laboratory of the Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage in Belgium
198 (<https://www.kikirpa.be>). Radiocarbon ages of these bones range from 4035±32 BP
199 (Lab# RICH-21772, ACAD14861, Cova des Màrmol, Bover et al., 2016) to 12,251±53
200 BP (Lab# RICH-21976, ACAD13139, Cova de Moleta). Published and unpublished
201 radiocarbon dates used in this study, along with their 2σ calibrated ranges BC, are listed
202 in Table 1.

203

204 **2.4. Library construction and hybridization enrichment**

205 Samples yielding positive results in our PCR screening and sample
206 ACAD13139) were used to construct genomic libraries in the clean-room facilities at
207 the ACAD laboratory. The library preparation protocol is based on the method by

208 Meyer and Kircher (2010) with modifications described by Llamas et al. (2016), in
209 which short P5 and P7 adapters (each P5 with a unique 5-mer barcode) were ligated to
210 the templates and heat was used to deactivate the *Bst* enzyme after the adapter fill-in
211 step. We used Platinum Taq Hifi (Invitrogen) for the first post-*Bst* PCR amplification of
212 the libraries, and Amplitaq Gold (Life Technologies) for subsequent amplifications.
213 Negative controls were included in each library preparation batch.

214 Mitochondrial genome enrichment of libraries was performed using biotinylated
215 80-mer (tiling 4x) RNA baits synthesized by Arbor Biosciences (MI, USA) as
216 described by Mitchell et al. (2016), and enriched libraries were pooled and diluted to 2
217 nM for sequencing. Enriched samples ACAD13066A, 13066B, 13066C, 14877A,
218 14878A and 14879A were sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq (Paired End, 2 x 150 bp).
219 The remaining enriched samples (ACAD13044A, 13059A, 13062A, 13063A, 13065A,
220 13067A, 13117A, 13139A, 14861A, 14876B, 14880B, and 14881A) were sequenced
221 on an Illumina HiSeq 2500 Rapid Run (Paired End, 2 x 100 bp).

222

223 **2.5. Sequence filtering, mitochondrial genome assembly, and authentication**

224 The raw fastq files were demultiplexed according to their P5 barcodes using
225 *sabre* v1.0 (<http://github.com/najoshi/sabre>), allowing one mismatch. The quality of
226 demultiplexed reads was assessed using *FastQC* v0.11.2
227 (<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc>). Adapter sequences were
228 trimmed with *AdapterRemoval* v2.1.7 (Schubert et al., 2016) with the following
229 options: mismatch rate 0.1, minimum Phred quality 4 (trimming bases with qualities
230 equal or below this value), quality base 33, and trim ambiguous bases (N). After
231 trimming, paired reads overlapping by at least 11 bp were collapsed into a single read,
232 and reads shorter than 25 bp were discarded.

233 As previous phylogenetic analyses placed *Myotragus* as sister taxon of *Ovis*
234 (Lalueza-Fox et al., 2000, 2002, 2005 a,b; Ramírez et al., 2009), we mapped a total of
235 2,797,334 collapsed reads from libraries made from extracts A, B, and C of sample
236 ACAD13066 to the *Ovis aries* mitochondrial genome (NC_001941). Mapping was
237 performed using BWA v0.7.13 backtrack algorithm (Li and Durbin, 2009) (with
238 options: -l 1024, -n 0.01, -o 2), and mapped reads with quality lower than a Phred score
239 25 were removed using SAMtools v1.3.1 (Li et al., 2009). Duplicate reads were filtered
240 using FilterUniqueSAMCons.py (Kircher, 2012). A 75% majority consensus sequence
241 was generated in Geneious v7.1.7 (Biomatters, <http://www.geneious.com>, Kearse et al.,
242 2012), retaining the reference allele at positions with read depth < 3. This consensus
243 sequence was then used as the reference for a new round of mapping following the
244 process described above, and another new consensus was generated. This process was
245 iterated until no additional reads could be mapped. After 15 rounds of mapping to the
246 *Ovis aries* mitochondrial genome, up to 53,466 unique reads were mapped covering
247 100% of the reference (including control region) with a mean depth of 278x. A final
248 75% majority consensus was then generated using Geneious, only calling nucleotides
249 for positions with a coverage depth ≥ 3 (other positions were called as N).

250 A second test of this iterative mapping procedure was repeated using the
251 mitochondrial genome of *Budorcas taxicolor* (NC_013069) as the initial reference.
252 Exactly the same consensus reference sequence was obtained for *M. balearicus* after 25
253 rounds of mapping to the *B. taxicolor* mitochondrial sequence.

254 The quality of the complete mitochondrial reference genome from ACAD13066
255 (100% covered at a depth of 278x using sequencing data from all three A, B, and C
256 extracts) was initially assessed using a BLASTn (Altschul et al., 1990) analysis of the
257 53,466 unique mapped reads, after which we visualized the results using Megan v5.6.3

258 (Huson et al., 2011). The results from BLASTn showed that all reads were assigned to
259 the eukaryote phylum, with most reads in the Bovidae family (see Fig. S1). In addition,
260 the mean fragment length of those reads was short (86.8 bp), as expected for authentic
261 aDNA. Analysis with mapDamage v2.0.2 (Jónsson et al., 2013) further indicated that
262 both the fragmentation and nucleotide misincorporation patterns (Fig. S2) displayed by
263 the mapped reads were consistent with typical aDNA damage (Briggs et al., 2007).

264 In order to further verify our consensus, we performed a *de novo* assembly of
265 collapsed reads from sample ACAD13066C (extract C) using default options in Ray
266 v2.3.1 (Boisvert et al., 2010). When we mapped the 16,811 contigs (123–11,127 bp
267 long) generated by Ray against our *Myotragus balearicus* consensus using the
268 Geneious mapping tool (medium sensitivity option), 15 were successfully mapped.
269 After removal of contigs shorter than 200 bp, 3 overlapping contigs were finally
270 obtained of length 11,127, 4,129 and 3,562 nucleotides, respectively. The scaffold
271 sequence obtained after aligning these three contigs was exactly the same as the *M.*
272 *balearicus* mitochondrial genome obtained using the iterative BWA mapping method
273 described above.

274 We annotated the *M. balearicus* mitochondrial genome using the Mitos Web
275 Server (Bernt et al., 2013; default options were used except for a cutoff of 30 and
276 start/top range of 35). Start/stop codons were manually revised by visually comparing
277 to annotated mitogenomes from Bovidae in Geneious. The total length of the
278 mitochondrial genome from *M. balearicus* (sample ACAD13066 from extracts A, B &
279 C, GenBank accession number MK847862) is 16,657 bp in length and includes 13
280 protein-coding genes (PCG), two ribosomal RNA genes (rRNA), 22 transfer RNA
281 (tRNA) genes and one non-coding control region (Fig. S3). All protein-coding genes
282 display the canonical start (ATG and ATA) and stop (TAA and TAG) codons, except

283 CYTB (stop codon = AGA), ND3 (stop codon = truncated, TA), and COX3 and ND4
284 (stop codon = truncated, T). The tRNA secondary structures of the *M. balearicus*
285 mitogenome, inferred using tRNAScan (Lowe and Eddy, 1997), were in agreement
286 with the cloverleaf folding pattern except for trnS1, which lacks the DHU arm as in
287 most metazoans (Helm et al., 2000). The mismatches observed in the stem structures
288 were strictly conserved relative to tRNAs in sheep and goat (see Fig. S4).

289 After verifying and annotating our ACAD13066 consensus sequence, we used it
290 as reference for mapping the collapsed reads from our other *M. balearicus* samples. We
291 performed this mapping step using BWA (parameters as above). All the libraries were
292 mapped in a single step except sample ACAD14877A, which needed a second round of
293 mapping to complete a 54-bp gap in the control region. A final 75% majority consensus
294 sequence from each *Myotragus* sample was generated, calling only positions with depth
295 ≥ 3 (other positions were called as N) (Table S2). While we reconstructed at least
296 partial mitochondrial genomes from all 16 samples, we only used the 13 mitochondrial
297 genome sequences with >80% coverage for downstream analyses (GenBank accession
298 numbers MK847858 to MK847870).

299 MapDamage plots (Fig. S5) generated from the unique reads mapped for each
300 sample displayed the damage and misincorporation patterns typically observed in
301 ancient samples (Briggs et al., 2007), although these features were not clear in samples
302 with a low number of unique mapped reads (*e.g.*, ACAD13117 or ACAD14881). The
303 truncated pattern in the 3' end of sample ACAD13062's mapDamage plot is caused by
304 the trimming of this first nucleotide in all reverse reads from the HiSeq 2500 run, as the
305 FastQC analysis showed an spurious insertion of an adenine base ("A") in the 5' end of
306 all reads.

307 No eukaryotic DNA contamination was detected in any of the blank controls
308 across all batches of *Myotragus* extractions and libraries.

309

310 **2.6. Hybridisation enrichment efficiency**

311 Enrichment efficiency was assessed by shotgun sequencing the unenriched
312 libraries from the ten best *Myotragus balearicus* samples (ACAD13059, 13062, 13065,
313 13066 extracts B and C, 13067, 14876, 14877, 14878, and 14879) on a MiSeq run
314 (Paired End, 2 x 150 bp). These shotgun data were processed and mapped following the
315 BWA protocol described above. When comparing the number of reads mapping to the
316 mitochondrial genome with high mapping quality (>Q25) as a proportion of the total
317 number of reads for each library, the enriched libraries exhibited between 219 and 828
318 times as many mapped reads when compared to shotgun data (Table S3). When
319 comparing only uniquely mapped reads as a proportion of the total, the enriched
320 libraries exhibited between 6 and 145 times more mapped reads than the shotgun data.

321

322 **2.7. Phylogenetic analyses**

323 We aligned our ACAD13066 consensus sequence to mitochondrial genome
324 sequences from 33 extant members of Caprini, the extinct helmeted muskox
325 *Bootherium bombifrons* (Genbank accession number MH706732), and *Bos taurus* (as
326 outgroup) (Table S4). DNA sequences from each of the 22 tRNAs and the 13
327 mitochondrial protein-coding genes (PCGs) were individually aligned with MUSCLE
328 (we removed all stop codons from the end of the PCG genes). Ribosomal RNA (rRNA)
329 genes were aligned using MAFFT v7.305b (Katoh, 2013). Loops and stems of both
330 rRNA and tRNA were identified using RNA-alifold (Bernhart et al., 2008).
331 Ambiguously-aligning regions of 12S and 16S genes were removed from the analysis

332 using default options in Gblocks v0.91b (Castresana, 2000). We then performed a Xia
333 et al. (2003) saturation test on 3rd codon positions for the full alignment and also for
334 each PCG alignment using DAMBE v7.0.5 (Xia, 2017), which revealed saturation in
335 some PCGs (Table S5). Consequently, phylogenetic analyses were performed on three
336 different datasets: 1) the complete alignment (Appendix 1); 2) the complete alignment
337 with 3rd codon positions of PCGs removed in order to eliminate the potential bias
338 arising from saturation (*e.g.*, Janke et al., 1994; Hassanin and Douzery, 1999; Phillips
339 and Penny, 2003) (Appendix 2); and 3) the complete alignment with 3rd codon positions
340 RY-coded (to minimize saturation bias while retaining some phylogenetic information)
341 (Appendix 3). As the results of some preliminary phylogenetic analyses suggested a
342 sister-taxon relationship between *Myotragus* and *Budorcas*, we created two additional
343 datasets to test their reciprocal monophyly: 4) dataset 1 with the addition of all
344 available *B. taxicolor* mitochondrial genomes (NC_013069, FJ207524, KU361169,
345 KY399869, and MH049869) and our ten *M. balearicus* sequences with less than 40%
346 of degenerate nucleotides (*i.e.*, ACAD samples 13059, 13062, 13065, 13066, 13067,
347 14861, 14876-14879) (Appendix 4); and 5) dataset 2 with the same additional
348 sequences as dataset 4 (Appendix 5). Our five final alignments (Appendices 1-5)
349 comprised either 11,434 nucleotides (for datasets 2 and 5; 7,526 from the 13 PCGs and
350 3,908 sites from the 24 RNA genes), and 15,197 nucleotides (for datasets 1, 3, and 4;
351 11,289 from PCGs and 3,908 from RNA genes). We inferred the optimal partitioning
352 scheme and substitution models for downstream analysis (Table S6) using
353 PartitionFinder v2.1.1 (Lanfear et al., 2016). For dataset 3, the RY-coded 3rd codon
354 positions were not included in the PartitionFinder analysis but instead considered as a
355 separate partition (with F81 nucleotide substitution model in the case of the MrBayes
356 analysis).

357 Phylogenetic analyses were conducted on all datasets under Maximum
358 Likelihood (ML) and Bayesian Inference (BI) frameworks using RAxML v8.2.11
359 (Stamatakis, 2014) and MrBayes v3.2.3 (Ronquist et al., 2012), respectively. Our
360 RAxML analysis comprised a ML search for the best-scoring tree out of 1000 bootstrap
361 replicates (-f a). Our MrBayes analysis comprised three heated and one cold Markov
362 chains running for 10^7 generations and sampled at intervals of 10,000 generations
363 (performed via the CIPRES Science Gateway; Miller et al., 2010). Convergence in
364 topology was assessed using the average standard deviation of clade (split) frequencies
365 (< 0.02), while convergence in individual parameter values was assessed through
366 effective sample sizes > 200 in Tracer v1.6.1 (Rambaut et al., 2014). Sampled trees
367 were summarized as a majority-rule consensus tree after discarding the first 10% of
368 trees as burnin.

369 We then calculated site likelihoods in RAxML for datasets 1, 2, and 3, and used
370 the Approximately Unbiased (AU) test (Shimodaira, 2002) as implemented in
371 CONSEL v1.20 (Shimodaira and Hasegawa, 2001) to test specific phylogenetic
372 hypotheses regarding the relationships among *Ovis*, *Oreamnos*, *Budorcas*, and
373 *Myotragus* (trees tested are depicted in Fig. S6.a).

374 Molecular dating analyses were conducted on datasets 1 and 2 using BEAST
375 v1.8.4 (Drummond et al., 2012), which co-estimates phylogeny and node ages, with the
376 optimal partitioning scheme and substitution models determined using PartitionFinder
377 (Table S6). We ran four independent chains for 10^8 generations each, sampling every
378 10,000 generations. We implemented a Birth-Death tree prior, a lognormal relaxed
379 clock model (with rate multiplier parameters for each partition), and each chain began
380 from a different starting tree. To calibrate our analyses we constrained two nodes in
381 accordance with the fossil record (following Bibi, 2013): 1) we constrained the age of

382 crown Bovidae (*i.e.*, the root of the tree) according to a normal distribution with mean
383 age 18 Mya and standard deviation of 1.0 My; and 2) we constrained the age of the
384 divergence between “pan-Caprini” and its sister lineage according to a lognormal
385 distribution with a mean of 1.274 (in real space), standard deviation of 1.0, and an
386 offset of 8.9 Mya. Parameter convergence was assessed through effective sample sizes
387 > 200 in Tracer. After discarding the first 10% of samples from each chain as burnin,
388 the trees from all runs were combined before summarising using TreeAnnotator v1.8.4
389 (Drummond et al., 2012).

390 We constructed a median-joining haplotype network (Bandelt et al., 1999) of all
391 13 *Myotragus balearicus* mitogenomes, excluding control region, using PopART v1.7
392 (Leigh and Bryant, 2015). After removing all alignment columns containing degenerate
393 nucleotides and Ns, a total of 3212 sites were analyzed of which 27 were segregating. A
394 maximum likelihood tree was also built from our alignment of *M. balearicus*
395 mitogenomes using IQ-TREE v1.6.5 (Nguyen et al., 2015) with the outgroup *Budorcas*
396 *taxicolor* (NC_013069). Node support was estimated by performing 1000 ultrafast
397 bootstrap replicates (Minh et al., 2013) with the best substitution model (as estimated
398 by IQ-TREE).

399

400 **3. Results**

401 The results of our MrBayes and RAxML analyses (Figs. S7, S8, and S9) are
402 largely concordant with the accepted relationships among extant caprines. In general,
403 the Caprini can be divided into the *Capricornis-Naemorhedus*-muskoxen clade
404 (‘Ovibovina; sensu Hassanin et al., 2009) and a clade including all other genera
405 (‘Caprina’ sensu Hassanin et al., 2009), with *Pantholops hodgsonii* basal to all other
406 Caprini. Our trees recover these nodes with high support (Posterior Probability [PP] =

407 1.0, ML Bootstrap [MLB] > 88). In addition, all caprine genera that were represented
408 by more than one species were found to be monophyletic (*i.e.*, *Capricornis*,
409 *Naemorhedus*, *Ovis*, *Rupicapra*, *Pseudois*, and *Capra*) in our analyses without 3rd
410 codon positions, although ML support is low in the case of *Capra* (MLB=70).
411 Conversely, monophyly of *Capra* is not supported by our analyses using the 3rd codon
412 positions, as has been observed in previous molecular phylogenetic studies using
413 complete or partial mitochondrial genomes (*e.g.*, Bibi, 2013; Zhou et al., 2019). Our
414 trees further agree with the attribution of “*Hemitragus*” *jayakari* to a different genus,
415 *Arabitragus*, as previously suggested (Ropiquet and Hassanin, 2005b). A sister-taxon
416 relationship between *Bootherium* and *Ovibos* was fully supported, as previously
417 observed by Campos et al. (2010), West (2016) and Bover et al. (2018b).

418 Analyses without 3rd codon positions suggest that the extinct *Myotragus*
419 *balearicus* forms a clade (PP=0.99, MLB=73; Fig. S7.a) with *Budorcas taxicolor* (the
420 takin), but this relationship is not well supported using the 3rd (PP=0.78, MLB=28; Fig
421 S6.b) or RY-coded 3rd codon positions (PP=0.92, MLB=54; Fig. S8). The *Myotragus*-
422 *Budorcas* sister relationship is in conflict with previous studies suggesting low to
423 moderate support for a sister-taxon relationship between *M. balearicus* and *Ovis*
424 (Lalueza-Fox et al., 2000, 2002, 2005a,b; Ramírez et al., 2009). Comparable topologies
425 and support values were recovered for the trees using multiple mitochondrial genomes
426 for *Budorcas* and *Myotragus* (Fig. S9), *i.e.*, support of clade *Myotragus-Budorcas* was
427 moderate (PP=0.98, MLB=76) when using dataset without 3rd codon positions, but poor
428 when using the dataset with 3rd codon positions (PP=0.91, MLB=48). In all analyses,
429 *Myotragus* and *Budorcas* were found to be reciprocally monophyletic with high support
430 (PP=1.0, MLB=100).

431 The results of our MrBayes analyses of the dataset excluding 3rd codon positions
432 suggested that *Ovis* is sister taxon to a clade comprising the remaining genera within
433 ‘Caprina’. However, within that clade, we were unable to confidently resolve the
434 relationships among clades formed by *Rupicapra*, a *Capra-Hemitragus jemlahicus-*
435 *Pseudois* group, *Ammotragus-Arabitragus*, *Oreamnos*, and *Myotragus-Budorcas*.
436 However, analyses of datasets including 3rd (PP=1, MLB=74) or RY-coded 3rd
437 (PP=0.98, MLB=52; Fig. S8) codon positions increased support for a clade comprising
438 *Rupicapra-Ammotragus-Arabitragus*. A lack of fully resolved relationships among the
439 major clades within ‘Caprina’ has previously been reported based on mitochondrial
440 data (e.g., Hassanin et al., 2009, 2012; Bibi, 2013; Yang et al., 2013), or even combined
441 mitochondrial and nuclear data (e.g., Ropiquet and Hassanin, 2005b; Shafer and Hall,
442 2010). Some studies has suggested a sister relationship *Ovis-Oreamnos* (e.g., Hassanin
443 et al., 2009; Zhou et al., 2019), but none of our results recapitulate this clade.

444 While phylogenetic analyses of our datasets excluding 3rd codon positions
445 support a *Myotragus-Budorcas* clade but not a clade comprising *Rupicapra* and
446 *Ammotragus-Arabitragus*, analyses including the 3rd codon positions decrease support
447 for *Myotragus-Budorcas* and increase support for *Rupicapra-Ammotragus-Arabitragus*.
448 Similarly, the AU test cannot reject a sister relationship between *Myotragus* and *Ovis* (p
449 > 0.05) when using the dataset with 3rd codon positions (Fig. S6.b), but this relationship
450 can be confidently rejected when using the dataset without 3rd codon positions ($p <$
451 0.05) or even tentatively when using the dataset with RY-coded 3rd codon positions.
452 This conflict suggests that multiple substitutions may have resulted in 3rd codon
453 positions becoming saturated, resulting in the erosion of phylogenetic signal at some
454 deeper nodes (see Janke et al., 1994; Hassanin and Douzery, 1999; Phillips and Penny,
455 2003). Indeed, the results of our saturation tests (Table S5) indicate while 3rd codon

456 positions are not saturated when using all the PCGs concatenated, 3rd codon positions of
457 nine of the genes individually display saturation (or are poorly informative) for fully
458 asymmetric trees. Concordantly, analyses of our dataset including RY-coded 3rd codon
459 positions (Fig. S8), which minimizes saturation while retaining some phylogenetic
460 signal, result in increased support for *Myotragus-Budorcas* relative to trees created
461 using the non-RY-coded 3rd codon positions (PP from 0.78 to 0.92, MLB from 28 to
462 54), and also decreases support for *Rupicapra-Ammotragus-Arabitragus* (PP from 1 to
463 0.98, MLB from 74 to 52).

464 The topology of our time-calibrated phylogenies, performed using BEAST (Fig.
465 2), were largely concordant with our MrBayes and RAxML results. For example, the
466 *Budorcas-Myotragus* sister relationship was moderately supported using the dataset
467 without 3rd codon positions (PP=0.91; Fig. 2.a), but poorly supported using 3rd codon
468 positions (PP=0.55; Fig. 2.b). The node ages we estimated are generally in agreement
469 with the published elsewhere for comparable nodes (*e.g.*, Ropiquet and Hassanin,
470 2005a,b; Bibi, 2013). We estimated the mean age of the split between *Myotragus* and
471 *Budorcas* as either 7.22 Mya (95% Highest Posterior Density, HPD = 5.5 – 9.21) for
472 the dataset without 3rd codon positions, or 7.08 Mya (95% Highest Posterior Density,
473 HPD = 5.79-8.57) for the dataset with 3rd codon positions.

474 Haplotype analyses of our 13 *M. balearicus* mitochondrial genomes yielded a
475 nucleotide diversity level of $\pi=0.00197$. However, the results of our network and
476 maximum likelihood phylogenetic analyses did not reveal strong signals of
477 phylogeographic structure, even when radiocarbon ages and deposit metadata were
478 included (Fig. 3). Nevertheless, most of the samples from Coveta des Gorgs (except
479 ACAD14878) grouped in a well-supported clade (with a bootstrap support of 97%),
480 which also included sample ACAD13044 from Cova de s'Olla. Notably, the one

481 Coveta des Gorgs sample that did not fall with the other samples from the same deposit,
482 ACAD14878, was actually one of the youngest samples (4456 ± 33 BP). In addition,
483 sequences from samples ACAD14877 and 14879—with mean calibrated ages separated
484 by more than 2500 years—displayed just four mismatches out of 15,635 bases (if we
485 include the control region and excluding degenerate nucleotides). In contrast, complete
486 mitochondrial sequences of two samples from Coveta des Gorgs, ACAD14876 and
487 14877, which had similar radiocarbon ages (6588 ± 35 and 6594 ± 35 , respectively),
488 displayed 29 mismatches (two in rRNA, 14 in PCGs, two in tRNAs, and 11 in the
489 control region).

490

491 **4. Discussion**

492 We are able to reject a sister-taxon relationship between *Myotragus* and *Ovis*
493 with high support when excluding 3rd codon positions of protein coding genes. Instead,
494 *Myotragus* appears to form a monophyletic clade with *Oreamnos*, *Budorcas*,
495 *Rupicapra*, *Pseudois*, *Hemitragus*, *Ammotragus*, *Arabitragus*, and *Capra* (BEAST
496 PP=0.95, MrBayes PP=1.0, MLB=52), to the exclusion of *Ovis*. While analyses
497 including 3rd codon positions weaken support for several key nodes, including the
498 position of *Ovis* relative to *Myotragus*, our results suggest that many of these positions
499 are potentially saturated, which can result in reduced resolution at some nodes (*e.g.*,
500 Janke et al., 1994; Hassanin and Douzery, 1999; Phillips and Penny, 2003). As some of
501 our results contradict previous molecular phylogenetic analyses of *Myotragus*, we
502 compared our new high-quality mitochondrial sequences to the previously published
503 gene fragments. Most studies have used the *cytb* sequence published by Lalueza-Fox et
504 al (2005a) and found, variously: 1) a close relationship between *Myotragus/Ovis*
505 (Lalueza-Fox et al., 2000, 2002, 2005a,b; Ramírez et al., 2009) or 2) a largely

506 unresolved position of *Myotragus* within Caprini (Agnarsson and May-Collado, 2008;
507 Bibi et al., 2012). We observed up to 97 mismatches (8.5% divergence) between the
508 Lalueza-Fox et al.'s (2005a) sequence (AY380560) and the corresponding positions
509 (14,157-15,297) of our new mitochondrial sequence from sample ACAD13066. In
510 contrast, there were only 20 variable sites among our 13 *Myotragus* mitochondrial
511 genomes for the same region of the mitochondrial genome. Similarly, there are seven
512 mismatches (2.3% divergence) between Lalueza-Fox et al.'s (2005a) 305-bp fragment
513 of 12S rRNA (AY380561) and the comparable region from ACAD13066 (positions
514 598-902), whereas just 2 mismatches can be observed among our 13 *Myotragus*
515 sequences. These mismatches, along with previous suggestions of a close relationship
516 between *Ovis* and *Myotragus*, would suggest that Lalueza-Fox et al.'s (2005a)
517 sequences incorporated contamination from modern sheep, as domestic species (like
518 sheep) are common contaminants in laboratory reagents (Leonard et al., 2007).

519 Our results specifically suggest a sister-taxon relationship between *Myotragus*
520 and *Budorcas* (BEAST PP=0.91, MrBayes PP=0.99, MLB=73) when excluding 3rd
521 codon positions. This relationship is surprising given the disparate geographical
522 distribution of these two lineages (the Balearic Islands and the eastern Himalayas,
523 respectively), when other closely related caprins (*e.g.*, *Rupicapra*) are today distributed
524 on mainland Europe (including the Iberian Peninsula). However, the addition of
525 *Myotragus balearicus* to the caprine phylogenetic tree does not otherwise help to fully
526 resolve the uncertain relationships among caprine genera previously noted in the
527 literature. There is a general consensus that additional genetic data, likely comprising
528 multiple nuclear loci will be necessary to confidently resolve the caprine phylogeny
529 (*e.g.*, Lalueza-Fox et al., 2002; Bibi et al., 2012, but see Ropiquet and Hassanin, 2005b;
530 Decker et al., 2009; Shafer and Hall, 2010). Nuclear data will also help to clarify the

531 sister taxa relationship between *Myotragus* and *Budorcas*, and to identify any
532 incomplete mitochondrial lineage sorting, which is likely to afflict rapidly diverging
533 lineages (like the caprine genera).

534 The ages of nodes estimated from our calibrated BEAST analyses agree with
535 those obtained using complete mitochondrial genomes from extant taxa alone (*e.g.*,
536 Bibi, 2013). Furthermore, our split between *Myotragus* and its putative closest living
537 relative, *Budorcas*, at around 7.1 Mya (95% HPD = 5.5 – 9.21 or 5.79-8.57, depending
538 on dataset used) is compatible with the arrival of *M. balearicus* ' ancestor to the
539 Balearic Islands during the Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC; 5.97–5.33 Mya; Krijgsman
540 et al., 1999; Manzi et al., 2013). This divergence date is in agreement with the origin of
541 other endemic Balearic lineages thought to have arisen as a result of the MSC, such as
542 the shrew *Nesiotites hidalgo* (Bover et al., 2018a), the Balearic endemic *Podarcis*
543 lizards (Terrasa et al., 2004), the Balearic midwife toad *Alytes muletensis* (Arntzen and
544 García-París, 1995; Fromhage et al., 2004), the land snail *Xerocrassa* (Chueca et al.,
545 2017), and endemic trap-door spiders (Mora et al., 2017), among others.

546 The patchy and poorly understood fossil record of late Miocene caprines (*e.g.*,
547 Geraads et al., 2006; Khan and Farooq, 2006; Bibi and Güleç, 2008) does not allow us
548 to establish clear relationships between the Western European mainland caprines and
549 *Myotragus*, although a relationship with the late Miocene (MN10) *Aragoral mudejar*
550 was suggested by Bover et al. (2010). Interestingly, although the physical robustness of
551 the metapodial bone has previously been considered a diagnostic characteristic within
552 caprines (*e.g.*, Gentry, 1992), *Budorcas taxicolor* and *Myotragus balearicus* (and
553 *Oreamnos americanus* to a lesser degree) all display especially robust metapodials,
554 which is a similarity previously observed by Andrews (1914). The sister-taxon
555 relationship between *Budorcas* and *Myotragus* suggested by some of our analyses

556 would imply that the acquisition of extremely robust metapodials happened only once,
557 in the common ancestor of these genera. However, the oldest representative of the
558 *Myotragus* lineage, *M. palomboi* from the early Pliocene (Bover et al, 2010), only
559 displayed moderately robust metapodials, suggesting that especially robust metapodials
560 have evolved multiple times and are not diagnostic of a clade comprising *Budorcas* and
561 *Myotragus* (and potentially *Oreamnos*). Indeed, the more distantly related musk ox
562 (*Ovibos moschatus*) also displays robust metapodials. This would also complicate the
563 phylogenetic placement of a fossil bovid from the late Miocene (MN11-12) deposits of
564 Baccinello-Cingiano Basin in the Tusco-Sardinian palaeoprovince (Abbazi et al., 2008),
565 which also has moderately robust metapodials. Subfamily attribution of the Baccinello-
566 Cingiano bovid metapodial and the relationship between *Aragoral* and *Myotragus* will
567 need to be clarified with additional palaeontological data in order to shed more light on
568 the late Miocene biogeography of Mediterranean caprines.

569 Our network analysis of 13 *M. balearicus* mitochondrial genomes (Fig. 3)
570 suggested the persistence of closely related individuals in the Coveta des Gorgs area for
571 at least 3930 years (*i.e.*, between 4350 and 8280 cal BC). Population stability in the
572 Coveta des Gorgs area is also supported by the close genetic relationship (four
573 mismatches out of 15,634 nucleotides, including control region) between individuals
574 ACAD14877 and 14879, which cluster together genetically yet lived at least 2660 years
575 apart in time (5620 cal BC versus 8280 cal BC). In contrast, the larger genetic distance
576 (29 mismatches) between mitochondrial genomes of samples ACAD14877 and 14876
577 (both from Coveta des Gorgs), which were dated to only four years apart, indicated the
578 presence of more than one maternal lineage in the region at the same time.
579 Interestingly, sample ACAD14878, the youngest sample from the Coveta des Gorgs
580 deposit (4456 BP, 3340-3010 cal BC), does not cluster with the other (older) samples

581 from this same cave, but is instead related to sample ACAD13139 from Cova de
582 Moleta, which is the oldest sample analyzed here (12,251 BP, 12,490-12,030 cal BC).
583 This suggests that while some phylogeographic structure existed among *M. balearicus*
584 on Mallorca, this structure was likely not conserved over long time periods.

585 Unfortunately, since no more than one specimen from each of the other caves
586 (*i.e.*, not Coveta des Gorgs) yielded DNA, it is impossible to be confident of the extent
587 of phylogeographic structure among *M. balearicus*. Additional data from other
588 individuals spread across different parts of the island would be necessary to investigate
589 this further. Additionally, if future studies are able to successfully isolate DNA from *M.*
590 *balearicus* samples from Menorca, it may be possible to investigate the impacts of
591 Quaternary glaciations and consequent ephemeral land-connection between Menorca
592 and Mallorca on *Myotragus* populations during these periods.

593

594 **Data Availability**

595 Read data are available at the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) of the National Center for
596 Biotechnology Information web (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>) under study
597 accession number TBA. The mitochondrial genomes of *Myotragus balearicus* are
598 available in Genbank; accession numbers MK847858 to MK847870, and alignments in
599 Phylip format for each dataset are available in Appendices 1-5.

600

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1023 **Figure captions**

1024

1025 **Fig. 1.** Map of Mallorca showing deposits where *Myotragus balearicus* samples were
1026 collected. Blue circles represent deposits that yielded endogenous DNA, and red circles
1027 represent deposits that did not yield DNA.

1028

1029 **Fig. 2.** Calibrated Bayesian tree of mitochondrial genomes (excluding Control Region)
1030 of Caprini using datasets without (a) and with (b) 3rd codon positions. Circles in nodes
1031 indicate PP=1. Green (a) and red (b) bars reflect the 95% highest posterior densities
1032 (HPDs) for node age estimates. See Table S4 for accession numbers and Table S6 for
1033 partitioning scheme. The temporal extent of the Messinian Salinity Crisis (MSC) is
1034 marked in gray.

1035

1036 **Fig. 3.** Haplotype network (left) and Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree (right)
1037 built using our alignment of 13 *Myotragus balearicus* mitochondrial genomes. The
1038 colour of circles in the network indicates radiocarbon chronology (according to the
1039 legend), whereas the colour of sample names indicates deposit of origin. The grey-
1040 shaded oval in the network corresponds to the highly supported clade in the ML tree
1041 (also depicted in grey). The tips of the ML tree are labeled with the sample number and
1042 mean sample age (in calibrated years BP). See Table 1 for a detailed list of radiocarbon
1043 ages.

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1048 **Supplementary figure captions**

1049

1050 **Fig. S1.** Megan graphic displaying the results of BLASTn analysis of 53,466 unique
1051 reads from ACAD13066, which were obtained after mapping to the *Ovis aries*
1052 mitochondrial genome (NC_001941). Most reads were identified as belonging to
1053 Bovidae, and especially to the Caprini tribe, suggesting the absence of non-caprine
1054 contaminant reads.

1055

1056 **Fig. S2.** MapDamage report of the BWA iterative mapping of *Myotragus balearicus*
1057 sample ACAD13066 to the *Ovis aries* mitochondrial genome (NC_001941). The top
1058 four panels show the characteristic high frequency of purines and pyrimidines just
1059 before and after the reads, respectively. The bottom two panels show accumulation of
1060 5' C-to-T (red) and 3' G-to-A (blue) misincorporations. The patterns displayed agree
1061 with those typically observed for ancient samples.

1062

1063 **Fig. S3.** Right: annotated circular mitochondrial genome of *Myotragus balearicus*
1064 ACAD13066 (right). Left: table with details on gene length, base composition, and start
1065 and stop codon for each Protein Coding Gene (PCG). All features agree with the
1066 structure observed in other Caprini mitochondrial genomes.

1067

1068 **Fig. S4.** Secondary structure of tRNAs from the *Myotragus balearicus* mitochondrial
1069 genome. All tRNAs display the expected folding pattern observed in metazoans.

1070

1071 **Fig. S5.** Result of MapDamage analyses of reads from all *Myotragus balearicus*
1072 samples mapped to the ACAD13066 consensus. Substitution and misincorporation

1073 panels display the pattern typically observed in ancient samples, as for ACAD13066
1074 (see Figure S2), except for samples with a low number of mapped unique reads (*i.e.*,
1075 ACAD13117 and 14881).

1076

1077 **Fig. S6.** Approximately Unbiased (AU) test for ML trees using Caprini mitochondrial
1078 genome datasets including 3rd codon positions (RY-coded and non-coded) and
1079 excluding 3rd codon positions. (a) Trees tested. Taxa with different position in topology
1080 are marked in blue. (b) Table with p-values of AU test for each tree and dataset. In red,
1081 p-values rejecting topology of tree ($p < 0.05$), and in orange tree topology with p-values
1082 close to 0.05.

1083

1084 **Fig. S7.** Bayesian Inference and Maximum Likelihood trees using Caprini alignments
1085 of mitochondrial genomes (excluding Control Region) without (a) and with (b) 3rd
1086 codon positions. Topology of each tree based on the BI tree with differences in
1087 topology of ML trees depicted in gray. Circles in node indicate PP=1 and
1088 Bootstrap=100, whereas numbers indicate PP/Bootstrap values. Asterisks indicate
1089 nodes not recovered in ML trees. Genbank accession numbers are listed in Table S4
1090 and partitioning scheme in Table S6.

1091

1092 **Fig. S8.** Bayesian Inference (a) and Maximum Likelihood (b) trees using the Caprini
1093 alignment of complete mitochondrial genomes (excluding Control Region) with RY-
1094 coded 3rd codon positions. Circles in node indicate PP=1 (a) and Bootstrap=100 (b),
1095 whereas numbers indicate PP and Bootstrap values, respectively. Genbank accession
1096 number are listed in Table S4. Partitioning scheme was adding an additional partition to

1097 the scheme for dataset without 3rd codon positions (Table S6, and see Material and
1098 Methods for information).

1099

1100 **Fig. S9.** Bayesian Inference and Maximum Likelihood trees using Caprini alignments
1101 of mitochondrial genomes (excluding Control Region) without (a) and with (b) 3rd
1102 codon positions and including the available mitochondrial genomes in Genbank for
1103 *Budorcas taxicolor* and mitochondrial genomes of *Myotragus balearicus* obtained in
1104 this study with < 25% of degenerate nucleotides. The topology of each tree is based on
1105 the BI tree, and differences in topology of ML trees are depicted in gray. Circles in
1106 node indicate PP=1 and Bootstrap=100, whereas numbers indicate PP/Bootstrap values.
1107 Asterisks indicate nodes not recovered in ML trees. Support values in internal nodes of
1108 *B. taxicolor* and *M. balearicus* clades were removed for graphical purposes. Genbank
1109 accession numbers are listed in Table S4 and partitioning scheme in Table S6.
1110 Nomenclature "Ovibovina" and "Caprina" following Hassanin et al. (2009).

1111

1112 **Tables**

1113

1114 **Table 1.** Radiocarbon ages of the 13 *Myotragus balearicus* from which we obtained

1115 mitochondrial genome sequences with coverage > 80%. Years BP are uncalibrated.

1116 Calibration using IntCal13 (Reimer et al., 2013).

1117

ACAD#	Lab code	Deposit	Years (BP)	2 σ (cal BC)	Source
14861	RICH-21772	Cova des Marmol	4035 \pm 32	2840-2820 (1.7%) 2630-2470 (93.7%)	Bover et al., 2016
14878	RICH-21771	Coveta des Gorgs	4456 \pm 33	3340-3010	Bover et al., 2016
13067	RICH-21981	Avenc des Gorg Blau	5165 \pm 36	4050-3930 (87.7%) 3860-3810 (7.7%)	Bover et al., 2016
13062	RICH-21776	Coveta des Gorgs	5438 \pm 35	4350-4230	Bover et al., 2016
14881	RICH-21975	Coveta des Gorgs	6313 \pm 37	5370-5210	Bover et al., 2016
14876	RICH-21769	Coveta des Gorgs	6588 \pm 35	5620-5580 (17.1%) 5570-5480 (78.3%)	Bover et al., 2016
14877	RICH-21768	Coveta des Gorgs	6594 \pm 35	5620-5480	Bover et al., 2016
13044	RICH-21982	Cova de s'Olla	6909 \pm 40	5890-5720	Bover et al., 2016
13066	RICH-21395	Coveta des Gorgs	8372 \pm 40	7531-7346	Bover et al., 2018a
13065	RICH-21773	Coveta des Gorgs	8562 \pm 38	7610-7530	Bover et al., 2018a
14879	RICH-21974	Coveta des Gorgs	9164 \pm 42	8540-8510 (2.4%) 8480-8280 (93%)	Bover et al., 2018a
13059	RICH-21779	Avenc de Fra Rafel	9783 \pm 39	9305-9215	This paper
13139	RICH-21976	Cova de Moleta	12,251 \pm 53	12,490-12,030	This paper

1118

DEPOSIT NAMES

- 1- Cova de s'Olla
- 2- Avenc des Vi
- 3- Cova de Moleta
- 4- Avenc des Gorg Blau
- 5- Coveta des Gorgs
- 6- Cova de Son Llobera
- 7- Cova Llunyana
- 8- Avenc de Fra Rafel
- 9- Cova Estreta
- 10- Cova devora Cova de Cal Pessó
- 11- Cova des Garrover
- 12- Cova Soleada
- 13- Cova Estreta de Gabellí
- 14- Cova des Corral des Porcs
- 15- Avenc de Na Corna
- 16- Cova Nova
- 17- Cova de Fumassos
- 18- Cova des Moro
- 19- Coves del Pilar
- 20- Covota Grossa des Puig Gros de Bendinat
- 21- Coves des Màrmol
- 22- Cova des Penyal Blanc

(a)

(b)

Fig. S1. Megan graphic displaying the results of BLASTn analysis of 53,466 unique reads from ACAD13066, which were obtained after mapping to the *Ovis aries* mitochondrial genome (NC_001941). Most reads were identified as belonging to Bovidae, and especially to the Caprini tribe, suggesting the absence of non-caprine contaminant reads.

Fig. S2. MapDamage report of the BWA iterative mapping of *Myotragus balearicus* sample ACAD13066 to the *Ovis aries* mitochondrial genome (NC_001941). The top four panels show the characteristic high frequency of purines and pyrimidines just before and after the reads, respectively. The bottom two panels show accumulation of 5' C-to-T (red) and 3' G-to-A (blue) misincorporations. The patterns displayed agree with those typically observed for ancient samples.

Fig. S3. Right: annotated circular mitochondrial genome of *Myotragus balearicus* ACAD13066 (right). Left: table with details on gene length, base composition, and start and stop codon for each Protein Coding Gene (PCG). All features agree with the structure observed in other Caprini mitochondrial genomes.

	Position		Size (bp)	Base composition %				Codon		
	From	To		A	C	G	T	Start	Stop	Strand
tRNA ^{Phe}	1	68	68	41.2	19.1	16.2	23.5			H
12S rRNA	69	1,024	956	35.9	23.7	18.4	22.0			H
tRNA ^{Val}	1,025	1,091	67	34.3	23.9	16.4	25.4			H
16S rRNA	1,092	2,663	1,572	37.8	21.5	17.0	23.7			H
tRNA ^{Leu}	2,664	2,738	75	30.7	22.6	18.7	28.0			H
ND1	2,741	3,697	957	32.0	31.0	11.6	25.4	ATG	TAA	H
tRNA ^{Ile}	3,697	3,765	69	39.1	11.6	15.9	33.4			H
tRNA ^{Gln}	3,763	3,834	72	36.1	29.2	9.7	25.0			L
tRNA ^{Met}	3,837	3,905	69	29.0	27.5	17.4	26.1			H
ND2	3,906	4,949	1,044	37.1	29.1	8.2	25.6	ATA	TAG	H
tRNA ^{Trp}	4,948	5,014	67	34.3	19.4	19.4	26.9			H
tRNA ^{Ala}	5,016	5,084	69	39.1	21.7	10.1	29.1			L
tRNA ^{Asn}	5,086	5,158	73	31.5	30.1	15.1	23.3			L
OL	5,159	5,190	32	34.4	28.1	28.1	9.4			
tRNA ^{Cys}	5,191	5,258	68	27.9	23.5	19.1	29.5			L
tRNA ^{Tyr}	5,259	5,326	68	27.9	20.6	16.2	35.3			L
COX1	5,328	6,872	1,545	28.6	26.0	16.4	29.0	ATG	TAA	H
tRNA ^{Ser}	6,870	6,940	71	33.8	28.2	15.5	22.5			L
tRNA ^{Asp}	6,946	7,013	68	38.2	17.6	16.3	27.9			H
COX2	7,015	7,698	684	34.6	25.6	13.7	26.1	ATG	TAA	H
tRNA ^{Lys}	7,702	7,769	68	32.4	23.5	19.1	25.0			H
ATP8	7,771	7,971	201	39.8	27.4	7.0	25.8	ATG	TAA	H
ATP6	7,932	8,612	681	32.3	29.8	11.0	26.9	ATG	TAA	H
COX3	8,612	9,395	784	26.8	30.7	14.7	27.8	ATG	T-	H
tRNA ^{Gly}	9,396	9,465	70	34.3	21.4	14.3	30.0			H
ND3	9,466	9,812	347	31.1	30.5	12.1	26.3	ATA	TA-	H
tRNA ^{Arg}	9,813	9,881	69	40.6	13.0	11.6	34.8			H
ND4L	9,882	10,178	297	31.0	27.5	12.5	29.0	ATG	TAA	H
ND4	10,172	11,549	1,378	31.9	29.2	10.7	28.2	ATG	T-	H
tRNA ^{His}	11,550	11,620	71	39.4	14.1	11.3	35.2			H
tRNA ^{Ser}	11,621	11,680	60	33.3	26.7	15.0	25.0			H
tRNA ^{Leu}	11,682	11,751	70	41.4	14.3	17.1	27.2			H
ND5	11,752	13,572	1,821	33.8	29.5	10.1	26.6	ATA	TAA	H
ND6	13,556	14,083	528	43.0	29.9	7.0	20.1	ATG	TAA	L
tRNA ^{Glu}	14,084	14,152	69	37.7	23.2	13.0	26.1			L
CYTB	14,157	15,296	1,140	31.8	29.7	13.2	25.3	ATG	AGA	H
tRNA ^{Trp}	15,300	15,369	70	35.7	20.0	17.1	27.2			H
tRNA ^{Pro}	15,369	15,434	66	34.8	28.8	13.6	22.8			L
CR	15,435	16,657	1,223	31.7	27.1	14.8	26.4			H
TOTAL		16,657	16,657	33.5	27.2	13.3	26.0			

Fig. S4. Secondary structure of tRNAs from the *Myotragus balearicus* mitochondrial genome. All tRNAs display the expected folding pattern observed in metazoans.

Fig. S5. Result of MapDamage analyses of reads from all *Myotragus balearicus* samples mapped to the ACAD13066 consensus. Substitution and misincorporation panels display the pattern typically observed in ancient samples, as for ACAD13066 (see Figure S2), except for samples with a low number of mapped unique reads (*i.e.*, ACAD13117 and 14881).

Fig. S6. Approximately Unbiased (AU) test for ML trees using Caprini mitochondrial genome datasets including 3rd codon positions (RY-coded and non-coded) and excluding 3rd codon positions. (a) Trees tested. Taxa with different position in topology are marked in blue. (b) Table with p-values of AU test for each tree and dataset. In red, p-values rejecting topology of tree ($p < 0.05$), and in orange tree topology with p-values close to 0.05.

Fig. S7. Bayesian Inference and Maximum Likelihood trees using Caprini alignments of mitochondrial genomes (excluding Control Region) without (a) and with (b) 3rd codon positions. Topology of each tree based on the BI tree with differences in topology of ML trees depicted in gray. Circles in node indicate PP=1 and Bootstrap=100, whereas numbers indicate PP/Bootstrap values. Asterisks indicate nodes not recovered in ML trees. Genbank accession numbers are listed in Table S4 and partitioning scheme in Table S6.

Fig. S8. Bayesian Inference (a) and Maximum Likelihood (b) trees using the Caprini alignment of complete mitochondrial genomes (excluding Control Region) with RY-coded 3rd codon positions. Circles in node indicate PP=1 (a) and Bootstrap=100 (b), whereas numbers indicate PP and Bootstrap values, respectively. Genbank accession number are listed in Table S4. Partitioning scheme was adding an additional partition to the scheme for dataset without 3rd codon positions (Table S6, and see Material and Methods for information).

Fig. S9. Bayesian Inference and Maximum Likelihood trees using Caprini alignments of mitochondrial genomes (excluding Control Region) without (a) and with (b) 3rd codon positions and including the available mitochondrial genomes in Genbank for *Budorcas taxicolor* and mitochondrial genomes of *Myotragus balearicus* obtained in this study with < 25% of degenerate nucleotides. The topology of each tree is based on the BI tree, and differences in topology of ML trees are depicted in gray. Circles in node indicate PP=1 and Bootstrap=100, whereas numbers indicate PP/Bootstrap values. Asterisks indicate nodes not recovered in ML trees. Support values in internal nodes of *B. taxicolor* and *M. balearicus* clades were removed for graphical purposes. Genbank accession numbers are listed in Table S4 and partitioning scheme in Table S6. Nomenclature "Ovibovina" and "Caprina" following Hassanin et al. (2009).

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. List of the Mallorcan *Myotragus balearicus* samples analyzed in this study, including deposit and municipality (in brackets). ACAD: Australian Centre for Ancient DNA laboratory number. IMEDEA: Institut Mediterrani d'Estudis Avançats collection number (samples labeled with an asterisk are from the Museu Balear de Ciències Naturals (MBCN) collection). M: upper molar. m: lower molar. "Weight" is the amount in mg of powder bone used in the DNA extraction step. Samples that yielded DNA in the PCR screening (PCR+) are indicated with "Y".

ACAD	IMEDEA	DESCRIPTION	LOCALITY	WEIGHT (mg)	PCR+
13040	59386	Vertebra	Cova des Garrover (Alcúdia)	200	
13044	58461	m3	Cova de s'Olla (Andratx)	220	Y
13045	6084	M2	Avenc des Vi (Andratx)	220	
13047	58582	Humerus	Avenc de na Corna (Artà)	180	
13048	6978	M2	Cova Nova (Artà)	190	
13050	58715	Tibia	Cova Nova (Artà)	250	
13053	65272	Femur	Covota des Puig Gros de Bendinat (Calvià)	180	
13054	6050	Radius	Cova Estreta de Gabellí (Campanet)	220	
13059	58238	Tibia	Avenc de Fra Rafel (Escorca)	210	Y
13060	80493	Humerus	Avenc de Fra Rafel (Escorca)	130	
13061	80506	M3	Avenc de Fra Rafel (Escorca)	200	
13062	5042	Femur	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	210	Y
13063	5052	Radius	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	190	Y
13064	5088	M3	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	230	
13065	60206	Mandible	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	230	Y
13066 "A"	81712	Tibia	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	210	Y
13066 "B"	81712	Tibia	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	100	Y
13066 "C"	81712	Tibia	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	110	Y
13067	58413	Tibia	Avenc des Gorg Blau (Escorca)	200	Y
13068	81715	m2	Cova Llunyana (Escorca)	170	
13069	sn	m3	Cova de Son Llobera (Escorca)	210	
13072	7282	Femur	Cova des Corral des Porcs (Lloseta)	220	
13077	58374	Radius	Avenc de Fumassos (Manacor)	210	
13080	1081	Radius	Cova des Moro (Manacor)	230	
13081	1663	Radius	Cova des Moro (Manacor)	170	
13082	4645	M2	Cova des Moro (Manacor)	160	
13083	10471	Radius	Cova des Moro (Manacor)	200	
13084	10473	Radius	Cova des Moro (Manacor)	230	
13085	43432	Radius	Cova des Moro (Manacor)	230	
13091	68176	M3	Cova des Moro (Manacor)	190	
13102	39072	M3	Cova des Mort (Cabrera)	240	
13103	sn	M3	Coves del Pilar (Palma)	180	
13107	1608	Humerus	Cova devora la Cova de Cal Pessó (Pollença)	180	
13111	44196	Radius	Cova Estreta (Pollença)	160	

13117	50086	Radius	Cova Estreta (Pollença)	230	Y
13120	50797	Radius	Cova Estreta (Pollença)	180	
13122	65919	M2	Cova Estreta (Pollença)	190	
13124	66008	M3	Cova Estreta (Pollença)	190	
13127	66077	M3	Cova Estreta (Pollença)	210	
13130	66514	Radius	Cova Estreta (Pollença)	190	
13137	59318	Tibia	Cova Soleada (Pollença)	210	
13139	sn (*)	Metatarsal	Cova de Moleta (Sóller)	210	See section 2.3
13141	sn (*)	Metacarpal	Cova de Moleta (Sóller)	210	
13143	sn (*)	Radius	Cova de Moleta (Sóller)	200	
14861	81610	Humerus	Coves des Màrmol (Calvià)	170	Y
14876	sn	Mandible	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	180	Y
14877	sn	Mandible	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	210	Y
14878	sn	Radius	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	130	Y
14879	sn	Sacrum	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	90	Y
14880	sn	Phalanx	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	170	Y
14881	sn	Phalanx	Coveta des Gorgs (Escorca)	170	Y

Table S2. Mapping and consensus sequence details for *Myotragus balearicus* mitochondrial genome sequences.

SAMPLE	READ DATA					CLONALITY	COVERAGE			
	Raw	Collapsed	Mapped	>Q25 Mapped	Unique	Mapped/Unique (%)	Mean Depth (x)	Std. Dev. Depth	Ref-Seq (%)	Mean Frag. Length (bp)
13044	1,575,452	1,449,785	6,579	6,579	520	0.92	2.6	1.6	91.4	82.2
13059	1,386,494	1,321,420	12,925	12,916	1,741	0.86	7.4	3.7	98.3	70.6
13062	1,595,332	1,440,846	168,893	168,801	6,383	0.96	30.9	9.3	99.99	80.6
13063	1,946,109	1,509,809	1,445	1,445	227	0.84	1.1	1.1	63.9	77.9
13065	1,163,963	1,004,679	72,674	72,653	5,159	0.92	28.4	9.7	99.97	91.8
13066 "A"	626,252	587,400	1,784	1,784	258	0.85	2.3	4.1	47.7	146.9
13066 "B"	965,939	918,157	39,730	39,713	20,792	0.47	101.9	36.7	100	81.6
13066 "C"	1,366,225	1,291,777	245,534	245,433	32,780	0.86	176	47.1	99.99	89.4
13067	1,712,201	1,600,622	9,380	9,370	823	0.91	3.7	2.2	94.6	73.9
13117	921,549	666,479	810	806	55	0.93	0.3	0.5	24.3	79.9
13139	1,704,044	1,486,475	17,125	17,123	590	0.96	2.4	1.7	87.4	67.1
14861	1,256,746	1,129,203	5,555	5,554	706	0.87	3.4	2.2	92.5	81.1
14876	1,096,616	772,645	102,598	102,595	1,270	0.98	6.4	3.2	99	84.1
14877	1,136,130	1,080,916	54,590	54,551	14,588	0.73	88.9	22.7	99.99	101.5
14878	798,308	657,867	13,307	13,303	1,648	0.87	9.8	3.9	99	98.6
14879	770,547	652,965	18,857	18,855	890	0.95	5.4	2.7	99.2	100.7
14880	1,203,725	510,326	17,152	17,151	157	0.99	0.8	1	54.2	89.2
14881	1,222,906	910,090	15,854	15,852	329	0.98	1.9	1.4	84.2	98.2

Table S3. Comparisons of reads mapped to the ACAD13066 consensus from enriched and unenriched (shotgun) libraries. Black case: data from enriched libraries (“enr”). Red case: data from unenriched libraries (“sho”). > Q25: reads with a mapping quality higher than a Phred score 25. “Ratio 1” is the X-fold difference between the % of “> Q25 mapped reads versus Raw reads” from enriched libraries and the one from shotgun libraries. “Ratio 2” is the X-fold difference between the % of “Unique mapped reads versus Raw reads” from enriched libraries and the one from shotgun libraries

ACAD	READ DATA									CLONALITY	COVERAGE			
	Raw reads	Collapsed	Mapped	> Q25 mapped	Unique reads	Q25 vs Raw (%)	Ratio 1	Unique vs Raw (%)	Ratio 2		Unique/mapped	Mean Depth (x)	Std Dev. Depth	Ref-Seq (%)
13059 enr	1,386,494	1,321,420	12,925	12,916	1,741	0.9316	628.2	0.1256	84.7	0.92	7.4	3.7	98.3	70.6
13059 sho	1,146,398	1,062,057	17	17	17	0.0015		0.0015		0.00	0.1	0.2	6.3	63
13062 enr	1,595,332	1,440,846	168,893	168,801	6,383	10.5809	304.7	0.4001	11.9	0.96	30.9	9.3	99.99	80.6
13062 sho	754,607	659,444	262	262	253	0.0347		0.0335		0.03	1	1.1	61.5	67.5
13065 enr	1,163,963	1,004,679	72,674	72,653	5,159	6.2419	381.9	0.4432	27.8	0.92	28.4	9.7	99.97	91.8
13065 sho	758,775	391,271	124	124	121	0.0163		0.0159		0.02	0.5	0.7	39.9	72.1
13066 “B” enr	965,939	918,157	39,730	39,713	20,792	4.1113	277.5	2.1525	145.3	0.47	101.9	36.7	100	81.6
13066 “B” sho	290,210	269,259	43	43	43	0.0148		0.0148		0.00	0.2	0.4	14.4	59.7
13066 “C” enr	1,366,225	1,291,777	245,534	245,433	32,780	17.9643	219.0	2.3993	29.4	0.86	176	47.1	99.99	89.4
13066 “C” sho	429,127	398,617	352	352	350	0.0820		0.0816		0.00	1.4	1.2	72.1	66.1
13067A enr	1,712,201	1,600,622	9,380	9,370	823	0.5472	235.2	0.0481	20.7	0.91	3.7	2.2	94.6	73.9
13067A sho	687,648	569,103	16	16	16	0.0023		0.0023		0.00	0.1	0.2	5.1	55.2
14876B enr	1,096,616	772,645	102,598	102,595	1,270	9.3556	443.1	0.1158	6.3	0.98	6.4	3.2	99	84.1
14876B sho	961,497	562,983	203	203	176	0.0211		0.0183		0.13	0.8	0.9	51.3	71.6
14877A enr	1,136,130	1,080,916	54,590	54,551	14,588	4.8015	436.7	1.2840	116.8	0.73	88.9	22.7	99.99	101.5
14877A sho	463,864	435,708	51	51	51	0.0110		0.0110		0.00	0.2	0.4	19.7	68.6
14878A enr	798,308	657,867	13,307	13,303	1,648	1.6664	682.8	0.2064	84.6	0.87	9.8	3.9	99	98.6

14878A sho	368,764	272,626	9	9	9	0.0024		0.0024		0.00	0	0.2	4.1	75.2
14879A enr	770,547	652,965	18,857	18,855	890	2.4470	828.6	0.1155	39.1	0.95	5.4	2.7	99.2	100.7
14879A sho	880,374	670,232	26	26	26	0.0030		0.0030		0.00	0.1	0.3	11.7	75.2

Table S4. Previously published bovid mitochondrial genome sequences used in our phylogenetic analysis. ‡ indicates extinct taxon. Additional *B. taxicolor* mitochondrial genomes were used in the analysis of sister-group relationship between *Myotragus* and *Budorcas*.

Species name	Common name	GenBank #	Reference
<i>Ammotragus lervia</i>	Barbary sheep	NC_009510	Mereu et al., 2008
<i>Arabitragus jayakari</i>	Arabian tahr	NC_020621	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Budorcas taxicolor</i>	Takin	NC_013069	Wu et al., unpublished
<i>Bootherium bombifrons</i>	Helmeted muskox‡	MH706732	Bover et al., 2018
<i>Bos taurus</i>	Cow	NC_006853	Chung and Ha, unpublished
<i>Capra aegagrus</i>	Wild goat	NC_028161	Zhang et al., unpublished
<i>Capra caucasica</i>	West Caucasian tur	NC_020683	Hassanin et al., 2012
<i>Capra falconeri</i>	Markhor	NC_020622	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Capra hircus</i>	Domestic goat	NC_005044	Hassanin et al., 2010
<i>Capra ibex</i>	Alpine ibex	NC_020623	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Capra nubiana</i>	Nubian ibex	NC_020624	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Capra pyrenaica</i>	Spanish ibex	NC_020625	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Capra sibirica</i>	Siberian ibex	NC_020626	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Capricornis crispus</i>	Japanese serow	NC_012096	Yasue et al., unpublished
<i>Capricornis milneedwardsii</i>	Chinese serow	NC_023457	Gong et al., 2016
<i>Capricornis sumatraensis</i>	Sumatran serow	NC_020629	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Capricornis swinhoei</i>	Taiwan serow	NC_010640	Lee et al., unpublished
<i>Capricornis thar</i>	Himalayan serow	KT345703	Zhang et al., unpublished
<i>Hemitragus jemlahicus</i>	Himalayan tahr	NC_020628	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Naemorhedus baileyi</i>	Red goral	NC_020722	Hassanin et al., 2012
<i>Naemorhedus caudatus</i>	Long-tailed goral	NC_013751	Jang and Hwang, 2010
<i>Naemorhedus goral</i>	Himalayan goral	NC_021381	Yang et al., 2013
<i>Naemorhedus griseus</i>	Chinese goral	NC_020723	Hassanin et al., 2012
<i>Oreamnos americanus</i>	Rocky Mountain goat	NC_020630	Hassanin et al., 2009

<i>Ovibos moschatus</i>	Muskox	NC_020631	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Ovis ammon</i>	Argali	NC_020656	Meadows et al., 2011
<i>Ovis aries</i>	Domestic sheep	NC_001941	Hiendleder et al., 1998
<i>Ovis canadensis</i>	Bighorn sheep	NC_015889	Miller et al., 2012
<i>Ovis orientalis</i>	Wild sheep	NC_026063	Lv et al., 2015
<i>Ovis vignei</i>	Urial	NC_026064	Lv et al., 2015
<i>Pantholops hodgsonii</i>	Chiru	NC_007441	Xu et al., 2005
<i>Pseudois nayaur</i>	Bharal	NC_020632	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Pseudois schaeferi</i>	Dwarf blue sheep	NC_016689	Zou et al., unpublished
<i>Rupicapra pyrenaica</i>	Pyrenean chamois	NC_020789	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Rupicapra rupicapra</i>	Chamois	NC_020633	Hassanin et al., 2009
Additional data			
<i>Budorcas taxicolor</i>	Takin	FJ207524	Hassanin et al., 2009
<i>Budorcas taxicolor</i>	Takin	KU361169	Feng et al., 2016
<i>Budorcas taxicolor</i>	Takin	KY399869	Liu et al., unpublished
<i>Budorcas taxicolor</i>	Takin	MH049869	Zhou et al., 2019

Table S5. Xia et al. (2003) saturation test on 3rd codon positions of each gene (a-m), as well as in the whole dataset [(n) 3rd codon positions, (o) all positions, (p) 1st and 2nd codon positions].

(a) APT6 – 3rd codon positions						(b) ATP8 – 3rd codon positions					
NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P	NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P
4	0.330	0.777	0.0000	0.762	0.0000	4	0.300	0.863	0.0000	0.959	0.0000
8	0.337	0.732	0.0000	0.631	0.0000	8	0.307	0.901	0.0000	0.902	0.0000
16	0.330	0.653	0.0000	0.458	0.0000	16	0.302	0.565	0.0000	0.569	0.0000
32	0.334	0.685	0.0000	0.364	0.2277	32	0.308	0.981	0.0000	0.895	0.0000
(c) COX1 – 3rd codon positions						(d) COX2 – 3rd codon positions					
NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P	NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P
4	0.354	0.796	0.0000	0.763	0.0000	4	0.367	0.777	0.0000	0.762	0.0000
8	0.358	0.753	0.0000	0.641	0.0000	8	0.374	0.732	0.0000	0.631	0.0000
16	0.349	0.723	0.0000	0.514	0.0000	16	0.364	0.654	0.0000	0.458	0.0006
32	0.353	0.704	0.0000	0.378	0.1124	32	0.366	0.685	0.0000	0.364	0.9329
(e) COX3 – 3rd codon positions						(f) CYTB – 3rd codon positions					
NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P	NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P
4	0.386	0.778	0.0000	0.758	0.0000	4	0.347	0.786	0.0000	0.756	0.0000
8	0.391	0.732	0.0000	0.627	0.0000	8	0.365	0.740	0.0000	0.629	0.0000
16	0.386	0.666	0.0000	0.464	0.0023	16	0.368	0.697	0.0000	0.488	0.0000
32	0.388	0.682	0.0000	0.356	0.1775	32	0.372	0.688	0.0000	0.359	0.4778
(g) ND1 – 3rd codon positions						(h) ND2 – 3rd codon positions					
NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P	NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P
4	0.345	0.782	0.0000	0.756	0.0000	4	0.314	0.783	0.0000	0.755	0.0000

8	0.359	0.735	0.0000	0.626	0.0000	8	0.326	0.737	0.0000	0.627	0.0000
16	0.350	0.683	0.0000	0.476	0.0000	16	0.320	0.688	0.0000	0.480	0.0000
32	0.354	0.684	0.0000	0.354	0.9925	32	0.328	0.685	0.0000	0.355	0.2028
(i) ND3 – 3rd codon positions						(j) ND4L – 3rd codon positions					
NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P	NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P
4	0.365	0.794	0.0000	0.824	0.0000	4	0.341	0.806	0.0000	0.850	0.0000
8	0.375	0.776	0.0000	0.711	0.0000	8	0.347	0.799	0.0000	0.748	0.0000
16	0.363	0.597	0.0000	0.470	0.0084	16	0.335	0.587	0.0000	0.486	0.0002
32	0.370	0.767	0.0000	0.520	0.0001	32	0.336	0.808	0.0000	0.592	0.0000
(k) ND4 – 3rd codon positions						(l) ND5 – 3rd codon positions					
NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P	NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P
4	0.380	0.793	0.0000	0.759	0.0000	4	0.363	0.802	0.0000	0.771	0.0000
8	0.387	0.748	0.0000	0.636	0.0000	8	0.370	0.761	0.0000	0.651	0.0000
16	0.379	0.713	0.0000	0.504	0.0000	16	0.365	0.738	0.0000	0.527	0.0000
32	0.382	0.698	0.0000	0.371	0.5295	32	0.368	0.713	0.0000	0.385	0.2839
(m) ND6 – 3rd codon positions						(n) ALL – 3rd codon positions					
NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P	NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P
4	0.328	0.778	0.0000	0.776	0.0000	4	0.392	0.849	0.0000	0.837	0.0000
8	0.337	0.739	0.0000	0.648	0.0000	8	0.400	0.842	0.0000	0.759	0.0000
16	0.326	0.631	0.0000	0.453	0.0001	16	0.393	0.827	0.0000	0.669	0.0000
32	0.332	0.701	0.0000	0.397	0.0290	32	0.399	0.809	0.0000	0.554	0.0000
(o) ALL – All positions						(p) ALL – 1st and 2nd codon positions					
NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P	NumOTU	Iss	Iss.cSym	P	Iss.cAsym	P
4	0.388	0.858	0.0000	0.846	0.0000	4	0.386	0.854	0.0000	0.845	0.0000

8	0.387	0.845	0.0000	0.762	0.0000	8	0.326	0.846	0.0000	0.766	0.0000
16	0.362	0.850	0.0000	0.676	0.0000	16	0.310	0.842	0.0000	0.680	0.0000
32	0.357	0.818	0.0000	0.572	0.0000	32	0.289	0.814	0.0000	0.570	0.0000

Table S6. Best partition schemes and substitution models for RAxML, MrBayes and BEAST analyses inferred using PartitionFinder. Partitioning scheme for dataset 3 (using RY-coded 3rd codon positions) is the same than for dataset 2 (without 3rd codon positions) but adding an additional partition ofr RAxML and MrBayes (using nucleotide substitution model F81).

Dataset 1 - WITH 3rd CODON POSITIONS (One mitogenome per species)		
Part	RAxML	
1	GTR+G	ATP6_1, CO2_1, CO3_1, CYTB_1, ND1_1, ND2_1, ND3_1, ND4L_1, ND4_1, ND5_1
2	GTR+G	12S_stems, 16S_stems, CO1_1, ND6_1, tRNA_stems
3	GTR+G	12S_loops, 16S_loops, ATP8_1, tRNA_loops
4	GTR+G	ATP6_2, ATP8_2, CO3_2, CYTB_2, ND1_2, ND2_2, ND3_2, ND4L_2, ND4_2, ND5_2, ND6_2,
5	GTR+G	CO1_2, CO2_2
6	GTR+G	CO3_3, CYTB_3, ND1_3, ND2_3, ND3_3, ND4_3, ND5_3
7	GTR+G	ATP6_3, ATP8_3, CO1_3, CO2_3, ND4L_3
8	GTR+G	ND6_3
Part	MrBayes	
1	SYM+I+G	12S_stems, 16S_stems, CO1_1, CO2_1, CO3_1, ND1_1, ND3_1, ND4L_1, ND6_1, tRNA_stems
2	GTR+I+G	12S_loops, ATP6_1, CYTB_1, ND2_1, ND4_1, ND5_1
3	HKY+G	16S_loops, ATP8_1, ATP8_2, tRNA_loops
4	HKY+I+G	ATP6_2, CO3_2, CYTB_2, ND1_2, ND2_2, ND3_2, ND4L_2, ND4_2, ND5_2, ND6_2
5	HKY+I	CO1_2, CO2_2
6	GTR+I+G	ATP6_3, ATP8_3, CO3_3, CYTB_3, ND1_3, ND2_3, ND3_3, ND4L_3, ND4_3, ND5_3
7	GTR+I+G	CO1_3, CO2_3
8	HKY+G	ND6_3
Part	BEAST	

1	TrNEF+I+G	CO1_1, CO2_1, CO3_1, ND1_1
2	GTR+I+G	12S_loops, ATP6_1, CYTB_1, ND2_1, ND3_1, ND4L_1, ND4_1, ND5_1
3	HKY+G	16S_loops, ATP8_1, ATP8_2, tRNA_loops
4	HKY+I+G	ATP6_2, CO3_2, CYTB_2, ND1_2, ND2_2, ND3_2, ND4L_2, ND4_2, ND5_2, ND6_2
5	HKY+I	CO1_2, CO2_2
6	TrN+I+G	12S_stems, 16S_stems, ND6_1, tRNA_stems
7	TIM+I+G	CO3_3, CYTB_3, ND1_3, ND2_3, ND3_3, ND4_3, ND5_3
8	TIM+I+G	ATP6_3, ATP8_3, CO1_3, CO2_3, ND4L_3
9	HKY+G	ND6_3
Dataset 2 - WITHOUT 3rd CODON POSITIONS (One mitogenome per species)		
Part	RAxML	
1	GTR+G	CO2_1, CYTB_1, ND1_1, ND3_1, ND4L_1, ND4_1
2	GTR+G	12S_loops, ATP6_1, ND2_1, ND5_1
3	GTR+G	12S_stems, 16S_stems, CO1_1, CO3_1, ND6_1, tRNA_stems,
4	GTR+G	16S_loops, ATP8_1, tRNA_loops
5	GTR+G	ATP6_2, ATP8_2, CO3_2, CYTB_2, ND1_2, ND2_2, ND3_2, ND4L_2, ND4_2, ND5_2, ND6_2
6	GTR+G	CO1_2, CO2_2
Part	MrBayes	
1	GTR+I+G	12S_stems, 16S_stems, CO1_1, CO2_1, CO3_1, ND1_1, ND4L_1, ND6_1, tRNA_stems
2	GTR+I+G	12S_loops, ATP6_1, CYTB_1, ND2_1, ND3_1, ND4_1, ND5_1
3	HKY+G	16S_loops, ATP8_1, ATP8_2, tRNA_loops,
4	HKY+I+G	ATP6_2, CO3_2, CYTB_2, ND1_2, ND2_2, ND3_2, ND4L_2, ND4_2, ND5_2, ND6_2
5	HKY+I	CO1_2, CO2_2
Part	BEAST	

1	TrNEF+I+G	CO1_1, CO2_1, CO3_1, ND1_1
2	GTR+I+G	12S_loops, ATP6_1, ATP8_1, CYTB_1, ND2_1, ND3_1, ND4L_1, ND4_1, ND5_1,
3	HKY+I+G	ATP6_2, CO3_2, CYTB_2, ND1_2, ND2_2, ND3_2, ND4L_2, ND4_2, ND5_2, ND6_2
4	HKY+I	CO1_2, CO2_2
5	HKY+G	ATP8_2, 16S_loops, tRNA_loops
6	TrN+I+G	ND6_1, 12S_stems, 16S_stems, tRNA_stems
Dataset 4 - WITH 3rd CODON POSITIONS (Multiple mitogenomes for <i>Budorcas</i> and <i>Myotragus</i>)		
Part	RAxML	
1	GTR+G	ATP6_1, CO2_1, CYTB_1, ND1_1, ND2_1, ND3_1, ND4L_1, ND4_1, ND5_1
2	GTR+G	12S_stems, 16S_stems, CO1_1, CO3_1, ND6_1, tRNA_stems
3	GTR+G	12S_loops, 16S_loops, ATP8_1, ATP8_2, tRNA_loops
4	GTR+G	ATP6_2, CO3_2, CYTB_2, ND1_2, ND2_2, ND3_2, ND4L_2, ND4_2, ND5_2, ND6_2,
5	GTR+G	CO1_2, CO2_2
6	GTR+G	CO3_3, CYTB_3, ND1_3, ND2_3, ND3_3, ND4_3, ND5_3
7	GTR+G	ATP6_3, ATP8_3, CO1_3, CO2_3, ND4L_3
8	GTR+G	ND6_3
Part	MrBayes	
1	SYM+I+G	12S_stems, 16S_stems, CO1_1, CO2_1, CO3_1, ND1_1, ND3_1, ND4L_1, ND6_1, tRNA_stems
2	GTR+I+G	12S_loops, ATP6_1, CYTB_1, ND2_1, ND4_1, ND5_1
3	HKY+G	16S_loops, ATP8_1, ATP8_2, tRNA_loops
4	HKY+I+G	ATP6_2, CO3_2, CYTB_2, ND1_2, ND2_2, ND3_2, ND4L_2, ND4_2, ND5_2, ND6_2
5	HKY+I	CO1_2, CO2_2
6	GTR+I+G	ATP6_3, ATP8_3, CO3_3, CYTB_3, ND1_3, ND2_3, ND3_3, ND4L_3, ND4_3, ND5_3
7	GTR+I+G	CO1_3, CO2_3

8	HKY+G	ND6_3
Dataset 5 - WITHOUT 3rd CODON POSITIONS (Multiple mitogenomes for <i>Budorcas</i> and <i>Myotragus</i>)		
Part	RAxML	
1	GTR+G	CO2_1, CYTB_1, ND1_1, ND3_1, ND4L_1, ND4_1
2	GTR+G	12S_loops, ATP6_1, ND2_1, ND5_1
3	GTR+G	12S_stems, 16S_stems, CO1_1, CO3_1, ND6_1, tRNA_stems,
4	GTR+G	16S_loops, ATP8_1, tRNA_loops
5	GTR+G	ATP6_2, ATP8_2, CO3_2, CYTB_2, ND1_2, ND2_2, ND3_2, ND4L_2, ND4_2, ND5_2, ND6_2
6	GTR+G	CO1_2, CO2_2
Part	MrBayes	
1	GTR+I+G	12S_stems, 16S_stems, CO1_1, CO2_1, CO3_1, ND1_1, ND4L_1, ND6_1, tRNA_stems
2	GTR+I+G	12S_loops, ATP6_1, CYTB_1, ND2_1, ND3_1, ND4_1, ND5_1
3	HKY+G	16S_loops, ATP8_1, ATP8_2, tRNA_loops,
4	HKY+I+G	ATP6_2, CO3_2, CYTB_2, ND1_2, ND2_2, ND3_2, ND4L_2, ND4_2, ND5_2, ND6_2
5	HKY+I	CO1_2, CO2_2

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